

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**“New Approaches in Crop Improvement for
Increased Climate Resilience”**

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CROPINNO Final Conference

“New Approaches in Crop Improvement for Increased Climate Resilience”

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SECTION 1

SOIL AND CLIMATE

ADVANCING SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS FOR CONTAMINANTS IN SOIL WITH CARBON-BASED AMENDMENTS

Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov,

Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski

*University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental
Protection, Trg Dositeja Obradovića 3, Novi Sad, Serbia, snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs*

Contaminated environmental matrices, particularly soils and sediments, continue to pose significant threats to ecosystem health, human safety, and the sustainability of land and water resources. This study explores the effectiveness of organic and carbon-rich amendments, including biochar, hydrochar, and compost-based materials, in reducing the risks associated with diverse organic pollutants. Controlled laboratory experiments indicate that these amendments enhance the sorption of contaminants by altering the physical and chemical characteristics of the matrices, thereby limiting pollutant mobility and bioavailability. This immobilization reduces the potential for groundwater contamination and uptake by biota. Furthermore, certain amendments promote microbial activity that facilitates the degradation of specific organic compounds, contributing to in situ natural attenuation processes. The research highlights how amendment properties such as porosity, surface area, and chemical structure govern their remediation performance. Mechanistic insights suggest that interactions between pollutants and amendments occur through hydrophobic partitioning, and surface complexation, which together control contaminant fate. Results emphasize the adaptability of these amendments, allowing for their selection and optimization based on the nature of the contamination and site conditions. Importantly, the use of waste-derived materials aligns with principles of sustainable remediation and circular economy by turning organic residues into valuable remediation tools. This work reinforces the potential of carbon-based amendments in improving the environmental safety of polluted matrices and supports their integration into future nature-based remediation frameworks.

Keywords: Environmental remediation, carbon-based amendments, pollutant bioavailability, sorption mechanisms, biodegradation, sustainable remediation

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